

Resveratrol attenuates the nephrotoxic effects of new Pt(IV) complexes by modulating the activity of components of the glutathione redox cycle

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Cisplatin is a widely used chemotherapy medication, but its usage is limited due to its low effectiveness and side effects on healthy tissues. That's why the investigations are directed at synthesizing new, like platinum complexes, or compounds obtained from natural sources as potential antitumor medications. This study aimed to assess the nephroprotection capacity of resveratrol (Res) in Wistar albino rats that had been exposed to new platinum(IV) complexes containing ethyl-, propyl- and butyl- esters of ethylenediamine-N,N'-di-S,S-(2,2'dibenzyl) acetic acid (C1, C2 and C3, respectively) through measuring the activities of components of the glutathione redox cycle in renal tissue: glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), glutathione reductase (GR), and glutathione-S-transferase (GST), reduced (GSH) and oxidized glutathione (GSSG). The animals were randomly allocated into eight experimental groups. The investigated compounds were given intraperitoneally as a single dose of Res (25 mg/kg) or Pt(IV) complexes C1, C2 and C3 (10 mg/kg), either separately or in combination, whereas the control animals received an injection of saline. After complex treatments, all enzyme activities (except GR) and GSH concentration were increased compared to the control, while the concentration of GSSG was decreased. Combined treatments induced a decline in GSH-Px activity and GSSG concentration, while GR activity was increased compared to complexes treated groups. The obtained results indicate that Res through GR-enhanced activity contributed to neutralizing GSSG, allowing the other components of the glutathione redox cycle to be more efficient in counteracting induced nephrotoxicity. These findings could be beneficial for further investigation of the precise acting mechanisms of the examined compounds.

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